

Autobiographical memories with emotional significance in architectural design conjecturing

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Abstract: This paper reports the results of an empirical investigation into the role of autobiographical memories with emotional significance in architectural design conjecturing. The empirical research consisted of a comparison of two case studies; three types of qualitative methods were used for data analysis. This paper describes the purpose of the use of autobiographical memories with emotional significance in design conjecturing as those memories emerge from an analysis of the talking aloud protocols used by the designers.

Key words: *design process, autobiographical memory, emotion, design conjecturing*

1. Introduction

It is no secret to any practicing architect that autobiographical experience is a resource for design [1-2]. Knowledge of technical information alone can't guarantee the ability to produce human-centric and meaningful work. What allows the architect to 'conceive,' to create an image and idea of a future place that makes us relate to it, love it, or hate it? It is the architect's life story that makes them who they are: developing into Selves through their experiences, their relationships with people and places, and the emotional connections and memories that stem from those relationships. The presentation of a task to an architectural designer should spark a process of "what-if" thinking [3], a realm of conjecture that naturally includes the designer's own experiences found in autobiographical memory. The design process, then, can be understood as a symbolic translation of an architect's experience into new, meaningful content [2].

In this paper, autobiographical memory is defined as it is in Conway [4]. Autobiographical memories, as compared to other types of memories (including autobiographical facts and episodic memory), are characterized by a high level of self-reference, the always present experience of remembering, personal interpretations, the long duration of memory, and context-specific sensory, and perceptual features, and imagery. Memorable experiences usually include an emotional component [4-6]. As a matter of fact, it is the emotions that determine the nature of autobiographical memories [4], and it is the emotional aspects of autobiographical memories upon which this paper focuses. Emotions are central to the meaning of experience because they are an expression of the way a person understands an experience [5]. Emotions and memory make us who we are; they are at the very basis of a person's Self, his or her value systems, beliefs and judgments. Autobiographical memory with emotional significance is defined here as memories that center on the thoughts, feelings and reactions of the

subject (in other words, around the source of emotions). This focus on the source of the emotion causes individuals to strongly personalize their account of the experience [6].

Place is central to remembering. Our memories are of places and in places. Architects design places for the future utilizing their autobiographical experiences with emotional significance through a construction of the architect as Self, through an understanding of place, and through shared meaning. This paper reports an empirical study into architects' use of autobiographical memories with emotional significance in design conjecturing. It specifically investigates the purpose of using such memories.

2. Empirical study

Two independently-conducted case studies were compared in this empirical research. One study was conducted by the author in the US, and the other study was generously provided by Peter Lloyd [7] and conducted in the UK. The first case study utilized an open-ended task, which was to design an office space for the author of the following haiku:

*Twilight cicadas -
The shadow of the pasania tree
Press on my desk.*

Designers did not receive any other information about their 'client.' In this study, the task was intentionally left open to interpretation, following the assumption that minimal requirements would solicit a more active use of autobiographical memories with emotional significance.

The second case study mimicked a real world situation with the researcher serving as the client, requesting an actual site and program. In a nutshell, the task was to design a nursery school for 3 to 5 year old children on a 1000 m² vacant lot in Sheffield, UK. A description of the activities to take place in the building and a breakdown of the interior space by area were both provided. The study design of comparing two case studies with different tasks, carried out independently by two different researchers, was chosen to eliminate biases made possible by the predisposition of the researcher or by the particularities of the participating designers. It is thought that adhering to this design added rigor to the study.

There were a total of twenty four participants in the empirical study. The participants in the first case study included fourteen architectural designers from around the US, who practiced in architectural firms or had independent practices. One criterion for choosing the participants was a five year active engagement in designing buildings. In the second case study, the participants included ten architectural students from the University of Sheffield, UK. Three of the students were sixth year architectural students, one was a fifth year student, and one participant had been in professional practice for over twelve years.

The participant designers were asked to talk aloud while they conjectured on the given task. Their talking aloud was tape recorded in the first case study and video recorded in the second case study. The recordings were independently transcribed by each of the researchers. Transcribed protocols were coded in order to maintain the confidentiality of the participants. Two sets of codes were used. For the US case study, "Participant #" was used to label the protocols. For the UK case study, the original coding labels created by Peter Lloyd were

preserved: “NA#” and “A#.” For this paper, the labeling is only significant for the citations used to illustrate the findings.

The methodology of this study has been discussed at length elsewhere [8] and will not be described in detail in this paper. In summary, three methods were used to analyze the data: direct analysis, indirect analysis and an analysis of affect in language using Whissell’s Dictionary of Affect in Language (WDAL) 2001 software [9].

Direct analysis is a phenomenological analysis of the raw data in its entirety. During the direct analysis, the researcher reviewed all of the data holistically, including the overall tone of the interviews, and any graphic information. A direct analysis of the data allowed the researcher to preserve the data’s complexity, to account for the designers’ sketches, and to focus on the larger themes and overall character of the monologue.

Indirect analysis is a qualitative analysis of verbal protocols for themes and categories using a sorting procedure. In this study, sorting was performed manually. All protocols were broken down into meaningful units (each unit containing one unique chunk of meaning or idea). Then units were coded to the protocol transcripts. Coded units were subsequently sorted and resorted until unit clusters and categories of consistent groups of meaning emerged. First categories, and then larger themes, were established. Overall, 45 categories and 16 themes emerged, several of which will be discussed later in this paper. The trustworthiness of the sorting was established through an inter-rater reliability. An external rater sorted ten percent of the units based on the definitions of each category and theme provided by the researcher. Cohen’s kappa was 0.61 for categories and 0.758 for themes.

An analysis of language for emotional coloring using Whissell’s Dictionary of Affect in Language (WDAL) [9] allowed for additional insight into how to interpret the data. WDAL is an instrument designed to measure the emotional meaning of words in text. To this author’s knowledge, this is the first time WDAL has been used for an analysis of the architectural design process. Since the use of autobiographical memories with emotional significance can be a subconscious practice, its use is not always evident from the protocols alone and can prove elusive during an indirect data analysis. For example, the analysis of meaningful units with WDAL allowed for a confirmation of the researcher’s insights regarding the positive or negative feelings of the participants, or the neutral tone of a unit. WDAL became an essential tool for making sense out of the data, and offered a number of unexpected discoveries.

3. Purpose of using autobiographical memories with emotional significance in design conjecturing

Multiple categories emerged from the data with respect to the purpose of the use of autobiographical memories with emotional significance during design conjecturing. The categories were consistent to both case studies, as well as to the individual designers, regardless of experience, task or demographics. The use of autobiographical memories with emotional significance was perceived as task-specific. This finding will be discussed in more detail further on in the paper. The purpose of the use of autobiographical memories with emotional significance in design conjecturing is presented below, and is summarized in Table 1. The subheadings refer to the purposes

that motivated the architects to use autobiographical experiences with emotional significance in their design conjecturing, and each section provides an example of such use as was made evident from the data.

Table 1. Summary of the findings

Purpose of use of autobiographical memories with emotional significance	Role of recall
Creating the feeling of place	Recall of a specific feeling of a place in order to recreate a similar feeling in the design
Construction of a metaphor	Reference to the embodied experience of design characteristics that allow conveying certain feeling
Use of a precedent	Recall of a feeling to be used as an analogy; memories of feelings are symbolically interpreted in the design
<i>Interpretation of a design task</i>	
Creating an atmosphere of a place	Remembering a specific place with similar typology or desired characteristics in order to inspire and shape design
Understanding the needs of a client or users	Recall of an experience of a place similar to the scenario in a design task in order to understand the atmosphere of the design to be created
<i>Personalization of a design task</i>	
The personal filter	Recall of an experience in order to understand the needs and preferences of a client or future users of a place
Primary Generator of Design Elements	Overall reinterpretation of the design task based on opinions, personal values and beliefs imposed on the design task
Beliefs	Choice of an element of a design task based on personal preference to facilitate the design
First Principles	Imposing a personal belief system on a design task in order to prioritize the program
Assumptions	Approaching the design based on personal design style regardless of the task at hand
About project	Reinterpretation of the design task as a whole based on personal preferences, experiences and values
About place	Creating a scenario for the place (location, place qualities) based on personal experiences
About client	Assuming the role of a client or assumptions made about the user based on personal experiences, values and beliefs.

3.1. Creating the ‘Feeling of Place’

When architects design, it is not only a form and a function of place, it is a ‘feeling of place’ or ‘atmosphere’ [10], and a meaning of place that they try to convey with the new places they create.

At twilight sound is hollow, at night it is mysterious. From when I was a kid I remember cicadas’ noise as very nice that I was falling asleep and waking up under. This is a little muggy, peaceful, mysterious Oregon memory (Participant 1).

In the quote above, the recall of the emotionally significant memory is clear. This memory from childhood allowed the participant to re-evolve a feeling she wanted to capture in her design for that brief. There are multiple similar examples in almost every interview, where the expression of memories allowed the researcher to vividly see how an architect recalls a feeling of place in order to create a similar feeling for the place they design.

Architects also look to the characteristics of places to help them create a certain ‘feeling of place.’ An example below demonstrates this:

The reason for the curve design, if you actually have a glazed curve then if you stand there, it feels like you're almost outside - it sort of blurs the distinction between inside and outside and it sort of just, [inaudible] and it's quite a welcoming shape, so when you come back in, it's very pleasant to walk into (Participant NA2).

In the quote above, the participant does not refer to a specific memory, but rather to an embodied experience of a curved, transparent shape. One can speculate that this was an autobiographical experience, this inviting feeling and connection with nature previously experienced in a transparent building, that allowed Participant NA2 to project their emotions and embodied experiences onto their design.

3.2 Construction of a Metaphor

So there is some kind of dynamics there just in the first phrase – “The twilight cicadas.” So I do not know what that defines, but I want to set up some kind of datum that expresses a dynamic movement across a certain rhythm (Participant 12).

As expected, this researcher found that architects use metaphors in their design conjecturing. The metaphor joins together reason and imagination [11]. In the example above, the architect recalled an autobiographical experience with emotional significance that he then used as a metaphor, even though ‘dynamic’ is really an embodied concept. Further on in monologue, other articulations support this assumption:

This dynamic rhythm of a place of contemplation, thought study. I guess, when I do design I make references to the experiences that I've experienced – whether this be the sound of the frogs or the cicadas, and light. Light is a major influence on my thought, the play of light and the play of time.

Lakoff and Johnson [12] wrote that we live by metaphors. Architects live and create by metaphors. This finding is not new, but the research presented in this paper supports this previously-known fact.

3.3 Use of Precedent

I was recently in a little place south of Paris a couple of weeks ago. And it was a building that has a kind of an intimate courtyard that has a diagram like this (Participant 8).

This is an obvious example of a direct utilization of a precedent to accomplish the research task. The participant recalled a place which that individual had visited recently and used the typology of that place as a diagram for his design, in order to capture a similar atmosphere.

3.4 Interpretation of a Design Task

3.4.1 Creating an Atmosphere of a Place

To understand the client and the kind of place to be designed, participants broke down their task into distinct notions or parts. Then they attempted to understand each notion or part, in order to grasp the most desirable qualities and the atmosphere of the design as a whole.

The pleasant images that came to my mind had mostly to do with a desk against the wall that had a window in it with light coming through. Also, I have a recollection of the painting I did when I was in graduate school and I wanted to do painting. I drew the window of the room and shadow coming in. It had a distinct sort of recollection for me (Participant 2).

The two notions from the design brief – twilight and desk – are apprehended by the designer through the recollection of an autobiographical memory with emotional significance, in this case a memory of a similar scenario involving an experience of light in an environment with a desk. This example is one of many where the memory of an experience assisted the designer in understanding the task.

3.4.1 Understanding the Needs of the Client or Users

There are two parts to each architectural task: (1) the physical, which involves the building itself and the program for that building, and (2) the human, which includes the client and the experiences of future users of the building. To understand the client and the client’s needs and preferences, architects rely on shared experiences through their autobiographical experiences with emotional significance:

At a studio, at a movie studio there are people that have different production deals or something. We just hired a producer, and when they are coming to the studio we have to create a space. And they are going to develop a movie based on that or whatever. So what kind of deal does this person have – is it like Steven Spielberg who is going to come work on the lot. Or is that people out of college, who wrote one hot script and who are going to come and we have to design space for them. So depending on what kind of deal they have - this is where politics come involved – because there is always reality to design process (Participant 9).

The example above is different from those quoted earlier. The use of the participant’s previous experiences is evident, but the emotional content of this experience is not clear. Working with people always involves emotions. Going into the field of politics in this case brings us to emotional intelligence, an obvious characteristic of Participant 9. Discussion of emotional intelligence is beyond the scope of this study, but one aspect of emotional intelligence should be mentioned: emotional awareness [13]. The next example is of almost the exact opposite. It is a clear reference to autobiographical experience:

Here is a lot of association with both images and words. Now I think that should be like a concrete shelter that is fully padded inside so you cannot hear the cicadas. Maybe the guy is absolutely insane because the cicadas were driving him absolutely crazy. All the childhood memories... They are all kind of jumbled; they are not distinct (Participant 1).

This excerpt from an interview with Participant 1 brings us to a discussion of another finding of the study: the personalization of the program. All participants made a significant number of assumptions about the project itself and the client. Those assumptions based on the architects’ experience, prioritizing the elements of the design task and certain decisions made during the act of designing, were reflections of the architect’s beliefs, values and experiences.

3.5 Personalization of the Design Task

Many years ago, Jane Darke [14] was one of the first researchers to write about the personalization of the design task. She expressed her discovery through her Primary Generator – Conjecture – Analysis model. In this model, the Primary Generator is defined as is a component of the designer’s cognitive structure, a subjective objective (or group of objectives) strongly valued, and usually self-imposed, by the designer that generates a design solution [14]. Other research later supported her discovery [2], [15]. Peter Lloyd [7,145] noticed that with experience, designers begin “to interpret the problem situation fitting it within their own procedural experiences of designing.” Designers first impose their own structure on the problem, which helps them control the situation. “The generally experienced designer has then made a transition in encapsulating his own personal preferences, judgment, and problem experience into procedural knowledge that can pre-structure novel design situations” [7,

145]. The study reported in this paper supports the finding that designers personalize their design situations. The following are examples of how autobiographical memories with emotional significance are used by architects to personalize their design situations.

3.6.1 Personal Filter

This is kind of part of the environment, it is very much a part of the environment. So, I think also that the client not always is a part of the environment. This space is elevated up in the air to see even farther than just where they are currently stationed, what they currently see. They can get up high and actually look around and be inspired by things beyond their immediate environment, kind of take it all in. And I think, this place is also very airy, without any walls. It's just an area of platforms up high in the environment.

The conjecturing by Participant 5 quoted above does not seem to be related to autobiographical memories with emotional significance, until one learns more about the participant. Other quotes from the post-task interview with this participant explain the more autobiographical elements:

Growing up traveling was probably the biggest impact on me. We had a motor home growing up. And so by age twelve I traveled forty eight out of fifty States, several times. We would take these summer vacations that are four-five weeks long, just travel through States. It was great experience just to see everything, it was fantastic. That includes like Canada, we went to Canada, saw a lot of outdoors, saw a lot, had a great life.

Are you going to go to Death Valley? Go see Death Valley. You got to. As far as anything, that's so different from anything else around. It's going to be hot this time of the year, but it's an amazing, it's shocking. I mean you'll never see such a wide-open landscape, and you feel so little in this big huge place. It's amazing.

From the above statements, it is clear that not only autobiographical experiences with emotional significance but also the personal values of the designer filtered into their design-conjecturing process. It is not possible to tell from the concurrent verbalization whether the utilization of autobiographical memories with emotional significance in the case of Participant 5 was conscious or intuitive. Later during the interview, those memories that floated into the participant's short term memory during the design exercise became conscious and were verbalized by the participant as they described their life.

Another way the designers filter the design task through personal preferences, values and beliefs was by paying more attention to certain parts of the design, or simply by imposing personal opinions on the project:

I think the building should be a bit more fun than just a like... (Participant A3).

For an experienced architect, phrases such as 'I like it' and 'it feels right' seem to be just as valid for judgments on or reasons for a decision, as would a logical and systematic rationale.

3.6.2 Primary Generator

Through the use of a Primary Generator, the designer limits an overwhelming number of project requirements to a handful that can offer him or her a way into the problem.

What if I was asked to design this desk? So the first thing, I suppose, I would do just as a base – I would use the numbers of five, seven, five [haiku structure] (Participant 5).

The first thing to ask you was about the site. I mean, are there any trees on the site? Because it's quite a leafy area (Participant A4).

The Primary Generator can either be given elements (like the site or the desk from the quotes above) or be of imposed personal *beliefs* (like the example below).

It's quite important I think to hear, seeing the children are so small, that there's nowhere where they can't sort of see outside you know where, for example here, they're too short to look out the window... (Participant NA2).

And that is not an urban setting. It cannot be an urban setting to me (Participant 11).

The Primary Generator can be an overall approach to design, called *First Principles* by Cross [16]:

I like to think of myself as a very analytical person, so I am going to approach cicadas in biological, anatomical approach (Participant 13).

Personal choice, or assumptions made about the project and the client that serve as a Primary Generator and a program, depend upon the structure of the design task. A comparison of the protocols of concurrent verbalizations in the compared case studies supports this statement. While in one case study the architects began creating a solution for the design task from working with *elements* of the site or a given program, designers in the other case study treated the task more freely, to the point of almost negating given requirements and creating their own:

When I am given a design task similar to this, really all I can do is take what little I have here and really create my own design problem, something that I am familiar with, instead of trying to piece together something that seems fairly nonsensical (Participant 13).

Another way the observed designers personalized their design situation was through assumptions made about the *place*, *client* and the *project* in general, based upon their own personal experiences and preferences. The types of assumptions made about the project in general, the space, and the client, were task-specific and task-dependent. In one case study, most assumptions were made about the place and the possible needs of the clients, while in the other case study most of the task requirements (including an understanding of the client and the task itself) were interpreted to reflect personal values and experiences.

Right now I am obsessed with our new house. It [my house] is solid and square with the big tree near it. We want to make an addition to it with a long walkway connecting it to the house. And now I thought that it may be something like that (Participant 7).

As we see from the excerpt, this designer personalized the *project* by literally making it their own – by calling upon the designing of their own house.

The majority of interviewed architects made assumptions about the *place* with which they were working. Previous examples showed how architects tried to understand and capture the ‘feeling of place,’ but they also made assumptions about where and what the place could be, based upon autobiographical experiences. In the example below, the designer called upon a memory of travel:

I say that [that place of design is not in the US] because I found from traveling...(Participant 10).

In the quote below, the architect attempted to understand their *client* by assuming his or her role, imagining themselves to be the person who wrote the haiku, working late at night with cicadas singing. For this participant, working late is a common situation, a vivid autobiographical memory with emotional significance involving working at a desk late at night, with the shadow of a tree falling onto his space, through the window, the door to the outside open, and the sounds of the bugs in the distance. The intimate memory allowed the architect to make an assumption regarding how the client would feel. The architect could then proceed to design a place that would capture that feeling.

And it is twilight, the shine is just breaking through, and there is still the last of the shadow, last of the shadow of the pasania tree. And the cicadas are singing because the light is coming. And then I am here and I am working on my desk, and I am pressing hard

on my desk, I am pressing hard on it. A thought or a vision, whatever that might be.
(Participant 12).

The more the design task leaves open to interpretation, the more autobiographical experiences and personal values and beliefs the designers bring to the design. Self and Designer are inseparable, and the self of the designer influences his or her design decisions.

4. Conclusions

To summarize the findings of this empirical study, it is important to state that the conclusions drawn are specific to the time and place, and to the participants, which is typical with qualitative analysis studies. The conclusions cannot be generalized to the entire architectural population. It is also necessary to mention that it became clear from an analysis of the language used in this study that the designers did not verbalize all of their thoughts and emotions during their interviews, which undoubtedly affected the findings.

This study allows researchers to tap into the purpose of the utilization of autobiographical memories with emotional significance during design conjecturing. It is known that autobiographical memories are a source for design conjectures; this empirical study brings us one step closer to understanding the specific purpose of the utilization of such memories.

The use of autobiographical experiences with emotional significance is task-dependent and task specific. The types of memories used reflect the design task. A comparison between the two case studies leads to the conclusion that the more open-ended and open to interpretation the design task is, the more that architects will use autobiographical memories with emotional significance to assist them in design conjecturing.

All architectural designers personalize the design situation. Autobiographical memories with emotional significance play a major role in such personalization. A designer imposes their personal values and beliefs on the design program by narrowing the requirements (as a Primary Generator) in order to begin conjecturing. Architects make a significant number of assumptions about their clients based on their personal experiences, the place for the design, and the project in general, in order to make a given project 'theirs.' There is still more to uncover with regards to autobiographical memories with emotional significance that are used both consciously and unconsciously (or intuitively), as well as with regards to design team interactions.

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6. References

- [1] Brawne, M. (2003). *Architectural Thought: The Design Process and the Expectant Eye*. Burlington, MA: Architectural Press.
- [2] Downing, F. (2000). *Remembrance and the design of place*. College Station: Texas A&M University Press.
- [3] Lawson, B. (1997). *How designers think: The design process demystified*, 2nd revised edition. Oxford: Architectural Press.
- [4] Conway, M.A. (1990). *Autobiographical memory*. Philadelphia: Open University Press.
- [5] Robinson, J. A. (1996). Perspective, meaning and remembering. In D. Rubin (Ed.), *Remembering our past: Studies in autobiographical memory* (pp. 199-217). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- [6] Christianson, S.A. (1992). Remembering emotional events: Potential mechanisms. In S.A. Christianson (Ed.), *The handbook of emotion and memory: Research and theory* (pp. 307-342). Philadelphia: Lawrence Erlbaum.
- [7] Lloyd, P. (1994). *Psychological investigations of the conceptual design process*. Ph.D. Dissertation, University of Sheffield.
- [8] Reference omitted in order to protect identity of the author for review purposes.
- [9] Whissell's dictionary of affect in language technical manual and user's guide, Available at <http://www.hdcus.com/manuals/wdalman.pdf>. [Accessed 5 May, 2008].
- [10] Zumthor, P., (2006). *Atmospheres: Architectural environments - Surrounding objects*. Boston: Birkhäuser Basel.
- [11] Cytowic, R.E. (1993). *The man who tasted shapes. A bizarre medical mystery offers revolutionary insights into emotions, reasoning and consciousness*. New York: Putnam Books.
- [12] Lakoff, G. & Johnson, M. (1980). *Metaphors we live by*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- [13] Working with emotional intelligence. Available at <http://www.irgworld.in/docs/Success/WorkingWithEmotionalIntelligence.pdf>. [Accessed May 20, 2008].
- [14] Darke, J. (1979). The primary generator and the design process. *Design Studies* 3, 157-162.
- [15] Israel, T. (2003). *Some place like home*. London: Wiley-Academy.
- [16] Cross, N. (2006). *Designerly way of knowing*. Boston: Birkhäuser Basel.